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Ergasheva Baxtiniso Uktam qizi

Qashqadaryo viloyati Koson tumani

24-umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktabi

ingliz tili fani o'qituvchisi

Annontatsion: *Purpose of mastering the discipline: acquisition by future specialists of fundamental economic knowledge, formation of logic of economic thinking and economic culture, teaching them basic methods of cognition and analysis of economic processes, ability to make sound decisions about economic problems related to their future; the formation of students integrated system of knowledge about future profession accountants intelligence, acquiring skills to navigate the successive stages of obtaining financial education in classical university, learning the basic concepts and categories of accounting and analytical science and practices to wide use acquired knowledge for competitive education in the first bachelor level.*

Task of the discipline: is to broadly acquaint students with the chosen direction in the field of accounting, audit and taxation; formation of modern economic and accounting-analytical thinking and skills for their further use in mastering a set of academic disciplines, which eventually form a full-fledged specialist in accounting and taxation; developing a critical attitude and the ability to navigate and use the theoretical principles of economic science and practice to successfully solve tasks, receiving a full education in the chosen specialty; gaining the ability to navigate the changing accounting and auditing environment, as well as apply the knowledge to solve specific situational tasks that will arise in the course of study in your chosen specialty.

Learning outcomes:

As a result of the course students should:

to know: a wide range of issues in the chosen field of accounting and taxation in general, a list of professional courses and special courses required for the formation of professional knowledge and skills, understanding of scientific ethics and academic culture;

be able to: properly navigate and use the theoretical principles of economics and practices for successful solving of tasks to obtain a complete education in the chosen specialty, to apply this knowledge in choosing priorities in the formulation and solution of specific practical problems; to reproduce the quoted text and to refer to the used literary sources in accordance with established requirements and standards; work independently creatively.

The content of the discipline is revealed in the following topics: Nature and major problems of the economy. The market and its driving forces. Market environment. Economic behavior of the consumer and the manufacturer. The role of the state in economic reproduction. Social Reproduction: A National and Global Dimension. University education in the context of the requirements of the European Higher Education Area. Professional training at KNEU: Characteristics of the specialty. Competent

“FORMATION OF PSYCHOLOGY AND PEDAGOGY AS INTERDISCIPLINARY SCIENCES” ITALIA

Approach to Teaching Disciplines. Academic virtue. Individual development planning. Introduction to the specialty training.

This academic discipline «Introduction to the Speciality» is a part of the Bachelor program of the «Applied Physics» speciality (specialization is «Physics of energy systems and novel energy sources»). It provides the general structure of education program, considers the power engineering structure and its operation, describes the modern trends and new directions in the power engineering. The discipline is taught in the 2d semester and includes six sections, such as «Introduction», «History of power engineering», «Energy resources supplies and energy effectiveness», «Modern and future power engineering», «Scientific and research complex of Ukraine in the field of power engineering». The discipline includes lectures (18 hours), seminars (9 hours) and overview home preparation. The report on this discipline is the test.

